

Table 2. GM-resistant reactions of Daquiqi and its hybrid progeny.^a GAAS, China.

Test Item	Parent and hybridized combination		Resistant plants (no.)	Susceptible plants (no.)	Resistant: susceptible	χ^2
Resistance of parent	Wanhuaai 1	-	0	70		
	TN1 (susceptible check)	-	0	80		
	W1263	-	73	2		
	Daquiqi	-	74	0		
Resistance heredity	Wanhuaai 1/ Daquiqi	F ₁	30	0	-	-
		F ₂	313	104	3:1	0.008
	Wanhuaai 1/ Daquiqi//Wanhuaai 1	B ₁ F ₁	40	47	1:1	0.563
Allelic relationship	W1263/ Daquiqi	F ₁	97	7	-	-
		F ₂	442	60	15:1	27.857
	W1263/Daquiqi// Wanhuaai	T ₁	66	19	3:1	0.317

^aP = 0.05, $\chi^2 = 3.84$.

132, 130, and 130 d; are 90, 83, and 93 cm tall; and yield 5.9, 7.0, and 6.6 t/ha in Guangzhou. Since 1989, they have been planted at 22 sites experiencing serious GM outbreaks in Guangzhou, Guangxi, Fujian, Jiangxi, and Hunan Provinces. Kangwen 2 and Duokang 1 were resistant or highly resistant to GM at all 22 sites, which represent different ecosystems with

different GM biotypes. Kangwen 1 was resistant in regions where only GM biotypes I and II occurred.

Resistance was evaluated with Chinese GM biotypes I and IV using the IRR screening method in the greenhouse and field. Seedlings and tillers of varieties were infested with GM adults and kept in nylon cages with three

replications. Resistance was evaluated as average of silvershoot frequency based on a random sample.

Reactions of varieties to GM biotypes differed distinctly (Table 1), but reactions to GM at seedling and tillering stages were similar. All varieties except Muey Nahng 62M and Ptb21 were resistant to Chinese GM biotype I. Only Kangwen 2 and Duokang 1 were resistant to Chinese GM biotype IV.

We analyzed the inheritance and allelic relationship of resistance to GM in varieties Wanhuaai 1 and Daquiqi, and cross W1263/Daquiqi. Parents and F₁, F₂, B₁F₁, and T₁ progeny were infested at seedling stage with Chinese GM biotype I. Silvershoots and healthy plants were recorded per hill.

Results indicate that Daquiqi, the resistant parent of Kangwen 2 and Duokang 1, has a single dominant gene for GM resistance (Table 2). This gene is nonallelic to gene *Gm-1* of W1263. We think that the resistance gene of Daquiqi is also not allelic to gene *Gm-2* of Leuang 152. Further study is needed. ■

Resistance to green leafhopper (GLH) in hybrid rice

R. Velusamy, Entomology Department; P. Jayamani, K. Thiygarajan, and M. Rangasamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We evaluated three hybrids and their parents for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant). Seeds of test lines

Reaction of hybrids and their parents to GLH.

Designation	Damage rating ^a
IR62829 A/IR10198-66-2 R	1 c
IR58025 A/IR10198-66-2 R	1 c
IR62829 A/Pusa 150 R	1 c
IR62829 A	3 b
IR58025 A	9 a
IR10198-66-2 R	1 c
Pusa 150 R	1 c
Ptb33	1 c
TN1	9 a

^aMean of 5 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

were sown in 40-cm rows 2-3 cm apart in wooden trays (60 × 45 × 10 cm) in a greenhouse. Ptb33 served as resistant check and TN1 as susceptible check. The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design; each breeding line was replicated five times. Seedlings were thinned to 15 per row at 7 days after sowing and infested with 5-6 2d-instar

nymphs per seedling. Plant damage was scored on a 0-9 scale when the susceptible check scored 9.

Hybrids IR62829 A/IR10198-66-2 R, IR58025 A/IR10198-66-2 R, and IR62829 A/Pusa 150 R and restorer lines IR10198-66-2 R and Pusa 150 R exhibited high levels of resistance to *N. virescens* (see table). ■

Screening rice accessions for resistance to thrips

R. Rajendran, M. M. Zainudeen, N. Raju, and K. Chozhan, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TRRI), Aduthurai, India

We screened 177 rice accessions from the All India Crop Improvement Project for resistance to thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) in the field at TRRI during Aug 1991 and 1992. Each test entry was planted in a 4-m-long row at 20- × 15-cm spacing. One row of susceptible check TN1 was planted for every 10 rows of test entries, with two replications. Damage was evaluated by

counting total leaves and damaged leaves in randomly selected plants at 25 d after planting. Mean infestation percentage was calculated and damage scored as 0-10% infestation = resistant (R), 11-20% = moderately resistant (MR), 21-50% moderately susceptible (MS), and 51-100% = susceptible (S).

Accessions BPT6038, BPT6881, BPT7325, KAU42-40-4-1, MTU11351, RP2333-59-25, RP2543-12874-286-1, and RP1746-12360-340 were resistant. Nine accessions were moderately resistant (see table). ■